

Indigenous Knowledge and Sustainable Management of Resources

Ajanta Das

Govt. Model Degree College, Barpeta, Assam

Corresponding E-mail : ajantadas.1998@gmail.com

In this study, the author explores the pivotal role played by Indigenous Knowledge (IK) in the sustainable management of resources, emphasizing the significant contributions of various indigenous tribes and communities. The author delves into the historical utilization of sustainable practices by indigenous peoples, showcasing their deep connection to the environment and the resulting benefits to ecological balance and broader sustainable development goals. Employing qualitative data and descriptive analysis, the author aims to elucidate the multifaceted dimensions through which indigenous knowledge informs sustainable practices in resource management. The author underscores the importance of indigenous tribes and communities, highlighting their demonstrated ability to harmonize economic activities with environmental preservation. Sustainable resource management practices by these communities have not only sustained ecosystems but also upheld cultural integrity and provided models for resilient economies. Recognizing and valuing these contributions becomes crucial for understanding and integrating indigenous perspectives into contemporary resource management strategies. The findings of the study have implications for sustainable development practices, offering insights into the efficacy of integrating indigenous knowledge into broader economic frameworks. The author argues that recognizing the importance of indigenous contributions can inform policy decisions, educational curricula, and collaborative initiatives that respect and draw upon traditional wisdom. By acknowledging the wealth of knowledge held by indigenous communities, the author contends that we can pave the way for more inclusive, equitable, and sustainable approaches to economic resource management, fostering a harmonious coexistence between communities and their environments. Top of Form